

Conductance studies of cupric chloride in aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose

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Limiting molar conductance of cupric chloride in aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K have been evaluated. Results have been interpreted in terms of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions, and structure making/structure breaking capacity of the solute from the temperature coefficient of Walden product i.e. $d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta)/dT$. Cupric chloride has been found as structure maker in aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose at temperatures 303, 308, 313 and 318 K.

The behaviour of electrolytes in aqueous carbohydrate solutions has recently been a subject of interest¹. The study of electrolytes in carbohydrate solutions is of great importance in the understanding of the physiological and biological processes associated with lives. Aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose are the chosen solvents as carbohydrate and related polyhydroxy compounds are the important constituents of biological systems. An understanding of the solution behaviour of aqueous systems involving carbohydrate and polyhydroxy compounds can be seen as an essential pre-requisite to a full understanding of the complex processes occurring in the biological systems.

Results and discussion

The limiting molar conductance Λ_m^0 for cupric chloride in different aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose solutions were obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of Λ_m versus \sqrt{c} to zero concentration. The limiting molar conductance of cupric chloride in 2, 4 and 6 percent aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K show that the limiting molar conductance increase with rise in temperature, which may be due to the increase in ionic mobility of free Cu^{2+} and Cl^- ions at infinite dilution. The Λ_m^0 values of CuCl_2 in aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose decrease with increase in carbohydrate (mannitol or dextrose) concentration. It may be due to increase in solvation and increase in association of CuCl_2 with increase in carbohydrate content. The Λ_m^0 has been regarded as a measure of solute-solvent interaction³, greater the magnitude of Λ_m^0 greater the solute-solvent interaction. The high and positive values of limiting molar conductance of CuCl_2 in aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose suggest more solute-solvent interactions at all temperature 303–318 K. The

Λ_m^0 values show that solute solvent interactions of CuCl_2 is comparatively more in dextrose than in mannitol.

The Walden product ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) as recorded in Table I increase with increase in percentage of mannitol or dextrose showing decrease in solute-solvent interaction in both cases, it is also confirmed from Λ_m^0 values for CuCl_2 in mannitol (Table I) which has the order : 2 > 4 > 6 percent and for

Table I. Limiting molar conductance, Λ_m^0 , Walden Product $\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ for cupric chloride in water and different aqueous mannitol and dextrose solutions at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Water	Λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ poise}$)
303		281.60	2.25
308		318.74	2.29
313		354.35	2.32
318		392.05	2.34
	2% Aqueous mannitol		
303		289.84	2.42
308		325.12	2.44
313		361.21	2.44
318		398.06	2.45
	4% Aqueous mannitol		
303		274.18	2.45
308		308.12	2.45
313		342.87	2.46
318		367.74	2.48
	6% Aqueous mannitol		
303		258.05	2.46
308		302.04	2.59
313		340.51	2.63
318		362.41	2.69

Table-1 (contd.)

	5% Aqueous dextrose	
303	339.89	3.29
308	420.05	3.33
313	463.21	3.42
318	495.40	3.45
	15% Aqueous dextrose	
303	299.69	3.66
308	358.71	3.67
313	387.90	3.74
318	423.92	3.97
	10% Aqueous dextrose	
303	329.90	3.64
308	405.21	3.61
313	453.12	3.65
318	485.92	3.66
	20% Aqueous dextrose	
303	271.89	3.77
308	315.91	3.94
313	360.05	3.99
318	374.51	4.13

CuCl_2 in dextrose has the order (Table 1) : 5 > 10 > 15 > 20 percent.

The temperature coefficient of Walden product i.e. $d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0)/dt$ is positive for cupric chloride in 2, 4 and 6 percent aqueous mannitol and 5, 10, 15 and 20 percent aqueous dextrose indicate that cupric chloride act as structure

maker both in aqueous mannitol and aqueous dextrose.

Experimental

Triply distilled water (sp. conductance = $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) was used throughout. Mannitol and cupric chloride were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared after drying them over anhydrous calcium chloride for 24 h or more. Solvents of various compositions were made by weight. Conductance and densities were measured at the desired temperature maintained with an accuracy of $\pm 0.05^\circ$ by methods described earlier². Standard deviations in density and conductance measurements were $\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{g cm}^{-3}$ and $\pm 4.0 \times 10^{-2} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

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